

Characteristics of Consumer Artificial Intelligence in Organisations' Data Analytics and Business Intelligence Processes

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ABSTRACT. This study examines analysts' perceptions on using consumer AI in data analysis and business intelligence. Introducing consumer AI in data analysis can make individuals more productive and efficient. However, some individuals fear how this innovation will change their employability. This study aims to determine which characteristics of consumer AI make it appropriate for use in data analysis that will increase an organisation's business intelligence. This study adopted an interpretivist philosophy to understand the nuances. Qualitative data was collected through semi-structured interviews with fifteen analysts. The results showed that the participants identified eight characteristics that make consumer AI appropriate for data analysis and business intelligence, namely: perceived ease of use, accessibility, rapid response, ease of interaction, mouldability, problem solving abilities and intuitive interaction.

Keywords: Consumer Artificial Intelligence (CAI); Artificial Intelligence (AI); Data Analytics; Business Intelligence; ChatGPT

1 INTRODUCTION

We are in the fourth industrial revolution where technology ensures unobstructed integration of multiple spheres, such as biological, physical and digital [1, 2]. A short time ago, self-driving cars, phones that talk, and applications that communicate as humans do were considered science fiction [3, 4]. Now, it forms part of everyday life and is performed so mundanely. These concepts are fueled by the compelling application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) [4]. For example, a self-driving vehicle uses multiple forms of AI, such as deep learning to ensure control over the vehicle based on information collected, image captioning and recognition to determine what objects are around the vehicle [5].

In recent years, AI has replaced many traditional jobs, job tasks and processes. Research has shown that automated processes can complete large percentages of job tasks that individuals, who earn high incomes perform [1, 6]. These jobs include senior managers, doctors and portfolio managers [1, 6].

The main objective of AI is to facilitate the interaction between humans and machines by simulating human intelligence [1, 7, 8]. The newest form of Consumer

Artificial Intelligence (CAI) is known as ChatGPT [9]. ChatGPT was only released late 2022 [9], and therefore academic literature about the platform and its capabilities regarding its analytical abilities is still in its infancy.

The volumes of data are so expansive that humans experience data deluge and, therefore, require cognitive systems to analyse the enormous amounts of data into clear and concise structured information that is easier for humans to make sense of [10]. When organisations implement data analysis, AI, big data, and machine learning to gain insight and ensure intelligent decision-making, intelligent automation occurs [3]. The main objective of this research study is to determine which characteristics of CAI the participants believe make it appropriate for use in data analysis and business intelligence.

The main research question to be addressed in this paper is: What specific characteristics of consumer AI will directly influence users' intentions to use consumer AI in data analysis and business intelligence processes?

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section provides a brief overview of important contextual concepts of this study. Section 3 provides a description of the research methodology followed for this study. Section 4 and 5 present the descriptive analysis of the participants and a discussion of the characteristics of CA. Section 6 discuss the findings and conclude the study.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Consumer Artificial Intelligence (CAI)

There are many different definitions of AI, including but not limited to, the use of computer science theories to create computer algorithms that perform tasks the same way a human would perform them [11]. Olan et al. [8] and Arakpogun et al. [7] indicated that AI is the use of IT applications that simulate a human's natural intelligence and experience to improve work processes and increase organisational efficiency.

Artificial intelligence is a big part of consumer's everyday devices [12]. Examples of AI-powered consumer devices are smartwatches [4] and Siri [3]. Therefore, the definition of consumer artificial intelligence is artificial intelligence devices that are targeted towards the everyday tasks of humans [13]. Humans must be trained to develop essential skills such as the ability to process different types of information, mathematical literacy and logical reasoning [1, 14]. These job tasks are fulfilled by individuals with relevant skills in mathematics, data science, engineers, accountants and technicians [1]. However, AI has the cognitive capabilities to perform these tasks in an automated manner.

Natural Language Processing (NLP) is another type of AI and occurs when computer applications have the ability to process, understand, interpret and react to natural human language [5, 9].

2.2 ChatGPT

In the technologically data-driven world we live in today, AI and other technological advancements have become a tool that consumers often use in business and their personal capacity [1, 15]. One of the most popular forms of CAI in recent months is Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer, universally known as ChatGPT [9]. ChatGPT is an Open AI chatbot platform that uses a language model that processes natural language requests and answers the prompt in a way like how a human would [9, 16].

Chatbots are applications where humans ask questions in natural language, and the Chatbot provides answers or engages with humans in natural spoken language [17]. Chatbots are used in many industries, including e-commerce and education and in processes such as information retrieval [17]. ChatGPT was launched in late 2022 [9] and reached one million users in less than five days [18]. A possible reason why ChatGPT might have become popular is that users can provide their commands in natural language, and ChatGPT can provide answers in the same type of natural language [17].

2.3 Big Data, Big Data Analytics and AI

A research study by Gupta et al. [10] indicated that since 2011 we have been in the cognitive era of computing, where the amount of data produced by the world has become too much for humans alone to process [19]. Therefore, the need for humans to use computers and analytical tools to make crucial decisions has increased drastically [10]. Ertemel [20] indicated that there are three V's that led to a big data revolution. These three V's are the amount of data in a dataset (volume), the intensity of the data production (velocity), and the different types of data in a data set (variety) [20].

In today's data-driven world, the amount of data organisations produce is more than they are capable of processing [20]. There is so much data to process in the world that humans experience data deluge, requiring cognitive systems to make sense of large amounts of data [10]. If data analysis is done manually, there will be fewer high-quality insights [20, 21].

When organisations have data, it is possible to create knowledge, and where there is knowledge, strategic decisions can be made [22]. With the enormous amount of big data, organisations can evolve in extreme ways [22]. However, analytics is needed to mine and analyse raw data to gain knowledge, information, and insight [20]. Analytics refers to using tools and techniques to discover hidden patterns and arbitrary relationships in data sets [20].

2.4 Business Intelligence

Organisations use business intelligence systems and processes to build new knowledge, enabling organisations to make informed decisions, identify gaps, provide customers with new products and services, and solve complex problems [23, 24]. Allam [25] defines business intelligence as using data, tools and frameworks throughout the business decision-making process and using strategies to collect, analyse and integrate the findings into their business, by presenting the findings to executives. Business intelligence

information assists the organisation in making informed and intelligent strategic decisions [25].

The process of gaining business intelligence starts with collecting, analysing and integrating all organisational data to visualise the current state of the organisation [24].

2.5 Characteristics of Consumer Artificial Intelligence

Cognitive ability. A research study by Canhoto and Clear [26] indicated that one of AI's most prominent characteristics is its cognitive ability. Especially AI applications such as machine learning can discover patterns in the data, learn from the data, and, as a result of past experiences, auto-correct mistakes [26]. Sangaiah et al. [27] defined cognitive computing as machines created with the core purpose of self-learning. An article by Haleem et al. [9] investigated the use of ChatGPT in multiple scenarios. One of the roles that ChatGPT could fulfil was the ability to have genuine conversations, provide outputs based on previous communication, and apologise when it provides incorrect information or misunderstands the prompt.

Natural Language Processing Ability. Popular tools, such as Python and Google BigQuery, facilitate data cleansing and mining and provide organisations with intelligent information [28]. However, some organisations might not have employees with the right skills and knowledge about business intelligence. Some organisations might not have employees proficient in data analysis tools at all [29]. These re-sources are also expensive to acquire [29]. Chatbots are an example of applications that use natural language to interpret and provide information [17]. CAI, such as ChatGPT, is a Natural Language Processing (NLP) algorithm that can react to commands written in natural language, interpret the request and provide the output in natural language. This functionality makes it very easy to use, therefore adding to its user-friendliness [30].

Analytical Ability. As discussed in previous sections, one of the main characteristics of AI is that it can analyse large data sets [1, 23]. Huang and Rust [31] indicated that AI has the ability to systematically adapt to changes in data sets as provided by the users. ChatGPT can process, analyse and synthesise copious amounts of data [9]. ChatGPT can turn unstructured data into structured data to mine for information and knowledge and can detect similar characteristics in different data sets to find patterns [9].

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research study aims to understand which characteristics of CAI make it best suited for data analysis and business intelligence processes. Therefore, the interpretivist research paradigm will be best suited. Interpretivist research aims to gather data and derive rich insights rather than provide evidence that can be seen as universally applicable, such as the positivist theory [32, 33].

This research study was completed using survey research. Survey research as defined by Check and Schutt [34] is the process of collecting data and information by asking questions to a sample of participants, analysing their responses and drawing conclusions to answer research questions [33, 35].

This research study used semi-structured interviews as the primary data collection method. Oates et al. [36] defined an interview as a structured, semi-structured or unstructured conversation between two or more people based on one main topic and consists of an interviewer and an interviewee. One pre-testing interview was completed and the feedback from the pre-testing interview was applied to the rest of the interviews.

The recommended number of interviews is 15-20 in-depth interviews [37, 38]. The interviews were conducted with individuals in particular roles, where their responsibilities included data analysis and business intelligence. Therefore, job roles such as data analyst, business analyst, business consultant, and IT management positions were approached.

This study followed all the necessary ethical procedures stipulated by the university, the faculty, and the faculty's research ethics committee. The interviews were audio recorded, and therefore, consent to record was required by all the study participants before the interviews commenced. The participants were informed that their participation was entirely discretionary, and they could decide to discontinue the interview at any moment without explanation [33]. The data was collected from individuals' personal experiences, not the collective experiences of an organisation.

4 DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

This study used qualitative data analysis as the text and script data collected from the interviews was analysed to better understand which characteristics the participants believe make CAI best suited for data analysis [33]. This research study uses a deductive or theoretical approach as it will provide a comprehensively detailed analysis of the data collected and because choosing the codes for the data analysis is based on the specific research questions that guide this study [39]. The data collected was analysed using thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is an analysis method used to analyse qualitative data by identifying patterns, sorting the data into the identified themes, and, in the final phase, conducting a report based on the identified patterns and themes [39]. The section below explains the thematic analysis process.

This study is exploratory; therefore, the researcher wanted to understand different individuals' opinions regarding the use of CAI in data analysis and business intelligence processes and determine how these individuals' different demographic details, years of experience, and education influence their opinions [32]. Fifteen participants were interviewed. The first participant was the test participant, and their data was not used throughout the study, but they provided valuable feedback incorporated throughout the rest of the interviews. The participants' years of experience varied from one year to twenty-plus years. The average years of experience was 8.5 years.

4.1 Participants Prior Knowledge of ChatGPT

Two of the fifteen participants (Participants 5 and 10) indicated they had not used any form of CAI, including ChatGPT, before the interviews. These two participants each had more than 20+ years of experience related to data analysis. Despite their extensive experience, Participants 5 and 10 had yet to use CAI.

4.2 Participant's Rate of Use

Six participants indicated that they used ChatGPT for the first time within a month of its official release, two participants indicated that they used it within three months of its release, two participants used it within six months of its release, two participants used it within a year of its release and one participant indicated that they used ChatGPT before its initial release through the use of an Application Programming Interface (API) [41].

4.3 Definition of Consumer AI

In previous sections of this study, the researcher wanted to define CAI. However, very few papers prior to this study provided a clear and detailed definition. Therefore, it was essential for the researcher to provide a straightforward, precise and structured definition. Each participant was asked to provide their definition of the phrase CAI. The participants provided a detailed definition of CAI and their interview extract. The interview extracts were analysed to define CAI and build on the definition of Saeedi et al. [13]. This definition of CAI will be used throughout this paper. Based on the analysis of the above participant's definition of CAI and the definition of Saeedi et al. [13], this paper defines CAI as: Large Language Models (LLM) using Artificial Intelligence (AI) chatbots, that the average consumer can use to improve how they act, behave, and perform in their personal and professional capacity. Examples include ChatGPT, Co-pilot, and Siri.

5 FINDINGS

The data revealed eight CAI characteristics that make it appropriate for data analysis and business intelligence. These seven characteristics are divided into two types: usability characteristics and intelligent characteristics. Each of these will be presented below.

5.1 Usability characteristics of CAI

The data has revealed six characteristics that speak to the usability of CAI in supporting DA and BI processes: perceived ease of use, accessibility, mouldability of CAI prompts, ease of communication and the intuitive nature of CAI. Each of these are discussed in the subsections below.

Perceived ease of use. The first characteristic relating to the use of CAI, that needed to be determined, was whether the participant found it easy to use. Interview data indicated that the participants perceived the interface of CAI as uncomplicated and not requiring a lot of effort on their part to use. Their expectation of how it would be to interact with CAI aligned with their prior experiences, reducing the need for extensive training. If individuals deem CAI easy to use, it might increase the extent to which users will adopt CAI throughout their data analysis and business intelligence processes.

All the study participants indicated they found CAI “easy to use”, “straight forward” and “easy to understand”.

For example, participant 15 indicated: *“I have found it easy to use. And given the fact that we're using it more and more extensively, and needed to adopt how I interact with AI”*. This quote not only illustrates how easy CAI was to use, but that continual upskilling is required.

Accessibility of CAI. CAI is very accessible. This study also stated that organisations can use ChatGPT to build applications with the use of ChatGPT without the need for incredibly high investment fees.

Participant 1 added this quote, *“Yeah so, what I would say is in terms of accessibility, I think anybody with access to a computer and some computer knowledge and know how, like, if you know how to use Google, for example, then I think you could definitely reap the benefits of ChatGPT”*. Participant 11 indicated that the accessibility of CAI is a very important and valuable characteristic. They added this quote, *“I think it's really accessible and quick”*. Three participants (Participants 1, 5 and 11) indicated that CAIs are very accessible to most users and, therefore, might influence a user's intention to use CAIs in data analysis and business intelligence.

Mouldability of CAI Prompts. Eight participants (Participants 1, 2, 7, 8, 9, 11, 14, and 15) indicated that CAI's ability to modify an answer based on user input is beneficial. For example, Participant 2 indicated that natural language mouldability makes CAIs very easy to use. They added an example: When requesting ChatGPT to generate a report based on a dataset, the user can change the requirements of the report continuously, which will make transforming data into information very quick. They added this quote, *“Yeah, the simple language ... makes it a lot easier that you can essentially type this is the report, you'll want to enter that it's mouldable, if I can put it that way. So if it produces a report ... you wanted to include specific things and you realise, okay, well I put in, and you can manipulate it and change it on the fly quite easily ... quite quickly to ensure that a report is built as required”*.

However, three participants (Participants 1, 14, and 15) also indicated that in some instances, the output could be manipulated to negatively affect the answers provided by CAI.

Ease of communication. Ten participants (Participants 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12) indicated that being able to communicate in natural language is one of the characteristics of CAI that makes it easy to use. Participant 11 added, *“Yeah, I think it's definitely*

easy to use ... So if I just put in a normal natural language, it most of the time understands what I'm asking for". This participant indicated that in their experience using CAI, the ability to provide input in natural language and receive output in the same manner was one of the most valuable characteristics of the innovation. Two participants (Participants 12 and 13) indicated that the ability of CAI, such as ChatGPT, to understand broken English is an essential characteristic. Participant 12 said: *"Yes, it's very easy to use because you type in your question. Whether your English is broken or not, it will understand you. It consumes that information and gives you exactly what you need. If it's not exactly what you need, you can always ask it again. Yeah, and it comes back with a different response. So it's a conversation. It's like, really chatting to a human being, but it's a robot programmed robot"*.

This essential characteristic of CAI makes it appropriate for data analytics and business intelligence.

Intuitive Nature of CAI. Three participants (Participants 2, 3, and 11) indicated that CAI has a level of intuition that makes using and extracting information from the chatbot easy. This section showed that three participants found CAI intuitive, making the innovation user-friendly and easy to use. However, participant 15 indicated that, for CAI to be more effective within an organisation, it needs to become an extension of the user and interpret and behave with more human-like characteristics.

Participant 11 indicated that they believe CAI is intuitive to a certain extent. They added this quote: *"And intuitive. Yeah, maybe it has some intuition in terms of the context. So if you ask a question about something, and then five questions later, you want to build on that you can, which is nice"*. They stated that CAI is intuitive to a degree as it can remember details the user provided in previous conversation sections

5.2 Intelligence characteristics of CAI

The data revealed two intelligence characteristics of CAI in supporting DA and BI processes: problem-solving and idea generation and rapid response of CAI. Each of these characteristics will be discussed in the sub-sections below.

Problem-solving and Idea Generation. Five participants (Participants 1, 3, 11, 12 and 15) indicated that due to the vast volumes of data the chatbots are trained on, even if they cannot flawlessly respond to a user's input prompt, it might give the user an alternate perspective on the complex problem.

Participant 14 indicated that they believe, based on their experience, that CAI is only helpful for basic analysis. The participant added this quote, *"I think for now, it can be used for more basic analogy, basic analysis. I think if you want to dive deep into your own company's data, you have to understand the processes behind it and the person that actually created the data points"*. The participant indicated that they believe a user still requires a great understanding of the data before any analysis with CAI can be done.

Rapid response. One of the characteristics of CAI that will be most effective for organisations and increase their performance is CAI's ability to answer questions almost instantly. Eleven participants (All participants excluding participants 1, 10, 12, and 13) indicated that using CAI in data analysis and business intelligence tasks will help them complete the task or achieve results much quicker than not using the innovative solution.

Four participants indicated that they believe CAI is best suited for tasks that are very repetitive data analysis. Participant 8 added this quote, *"The really boring stuff and the really repetitive stuff. So for instance, the data loadings, the ETL pipelines, the basic calculations that we run, and stuff like that..., that's where consumer AI will play the biggest role"*.

Participant 6 indicated that *"... the whole point of analysis is to get to an answer to a question and to a problem. So the quicker you can get to that answer, the better and quicker you can make decisions"*. Eleven participants indicated that using CAI in data analysis and business intelligence tasks will help them complete tasks rapidly, thereby increasing productivity.

6 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study aimed to determine which characteristics make CAI best suited for data analysis and business intelligence. The study participants identified eight characteristics, which they believe are important for the effective use of CAI in these areas.

CAI use within this study is positioned within a socio-technical system: human interaction with organisational processes using a technological system [40] in line with previous studies, for example, that investigated human-AI symbiosis [41] and an intelligent and hierarchical approach to the socio-technical nature of human-centered AI [42]. Figure 1 presents the conceptual model of how CAI is used in DA and BI processes. According to Quamar et al [43] conversation system for BI applications needs to be easy and intuitive, to ensure an increased user experience. This leads to improved productivity and efficiency as tasks as CAI supports repetitive tasks, basic calculations [44]. Supporting these DA and BI processes, make CAI suitable to support basic DA and BI processes, creating intelligent organisations [44]. This in turn supports organisational decision making [25].

Therefore, both the usability characteristics and intelligence capabilities of CA contribute to an enhanced experience for analysts. Completing a data analysis or business intelligence task quicker increases the user's job performance, productivity and efficiency, allowing them to focus on more important matters.

This research study focuses on organisations operating in South Africa specifically. Different countries and organisations have different rules and regulations relating to the use of CAI. The findings of this study contribute to the existing body of knowledge regarding AI, big data, big data analytics, and business intelligence. The information and results provided throughout this study provide details regarding ChatGPT just after it was launched. This provides future opportunities for researchers to use the findings and suggestions of this study to continue academic research relating to CAI.

Fig. 1. Conceptual model for CAI driven DA and BI

The participants identified eight characteristics that make CAI best suited for data analysis and business intelligence. This study contributes to the growing body of knowledge relating to rapidly evolving CAIs such as ChatGPT. CAI has become a part of most people's everyday lives and should, therefore, not be avoided but rather embraced to assist data analysts with ways to make them more efficient and provide greater information to organisations to improve decision-making.

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